

Original article

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MARKOV CHAIN MODEL FOR SPREADING RUMORS

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Abstract: *Mathematical models of the spread of rumors are a well established research subject, especially for their similarity with modelling the spread of infectious diseases. In particular, the problem of spreading of rumors in the finite group of people can be analyzed by means of discrete - time Markov chain, where a unit of time corresponds to the interval between two consecutive interactions between the individuals in the group. We slightly generalize the existing models by introducing the possibility of multiple sources of rumor (individuals who initially know the same rumor). The technique used for obtaining the distributional properties of waiting time until the rumor is spread in the group is based on computing the fundamental matrix of the corresponding Markov chain, which is suitable tool for dealing with several combinatorial scenarios in discrete time.*

Keywords: *Rumor spreading, discrete-time Markov chains, waiting time.*